

INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LAND MARKING AND MAPPING LAND USER BOUNDARIES

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Abstract. In various sectors of our country's economy, as well as the advantages of the correct application of modern innovative technological programs in the field of construction, including digital mapping of all regions, monitoring of geodetic works, in particular, the Geoinformation System and Technologies (GAT) program to the production sector. 2020 was named "Year of Science and Digital Economy Development". According to the appeal sent by our president to the members of the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, it is planned to implement a number of reforms for the development of the digital economy.

Keywords. Map, Geoinformation system, aerial photography, orthophoto planes, GPS, SASPLANET, geodesy, cartography.

Enter. On the basis of activities within the framework of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" program, it is planned to establish IT parks, further improve the "Electronic Government" system, and fully digitize the fields of construction, energy, transport, health care, archives, education, geology, agriculture and animal husbandry, and cadastre. was

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers on the improvement of the efficiency of the measures to determine the boundaries of administrative-territorial units, to carry out land resource surveying and to further improve the procedure for conducting geobotanical research in pastures and hayfields was approved.

In recent years, the use of digital technologies in the organization of rational and efficient use of land, regulation of land relations, and strengthening of state control over land use in our republic can achieve effective results.

Taking into account the above and in order to strengthen state control over the protection and rational use of land, to establish a systematic way of keeping accurate records of land resources, to increase the efficiency of the use of agricultural land, including irrigated, dry and pasture land, the Cabinet of Ministers of April 23, 2018, Decision No. 299 was adopted.

In this decision, the state inspectors of the State Committee for Land Resources, Geodesy, Cartography and State Cadastre of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the control of land use and its protection, regardless of the organizational and legal form, regularly monitor the use of land allocated to them by land users (without interfering with financial economic activities). has the right to monitor. In 2018-2019, using the KOMPSAT-3 and KOMPSAT-3A satellites of the Republic of Korea, space images covering the entire territory of the Republic were taken, and 5,712 (100%) on a scale of 1:10,000 for irrigated lands and settlements and the rest of the Republic (mountainous, mountainous and 3,608 (100%) 9,320 orthophotoplanes on a scale of 1:25,000 were created for desert) areas.

In order to take account of real estate and demarcate irrigated lands, aerial photography was carried out in the regions of Kashkadarya, Tashkent, Khorezm and Tashkent city.

6,724 1:2,000-scale and 387 1:10,000-scale orthophoto plans were created using aerial photos. (Fig. 1)/

Coordinate system is very important in orthophotoplanes. The state coordinate system was recalculated to Gauss-Kruger flat rectangular coordinates based on the determined data. The geodetic coordinate system of 1942, the coordinates of the points relative to the starting point adopted in the state coordinate system.

obtained from orthophotoplanes is 95%. The resolution within each pixel cell is 0.5 m. should be equal to (Figure 3). However, annual or monthly purchase of orthophotoplanes from abroad, i.e. from Korea, China, Russian Federation, harms the state budget. Therefore, it is possible to obtain data for every 6 months of the year using the SASPLANET program from another program.

In this case, we can get a current view of the place with the help of the SASPLANET program. The advantage of this program is that it downloads the downloaded raster data to its cache in the formats "map, dat, kml, tab, w, w (short ext)". (Figure 4)

Working in this way creates a number of advantages and conveniences for specialists in the fields of geodesy, cartography and cadastre in our field.

When downloading from the SASPLANET program, we need to choose the correct projections and coordinates for the correct and high-resolution placement in the GISS program.

Свойство	Значение
Информация о растре	
Столбцы и строки	9190, 8103
Число каналов	3
Размер ячейки (X, Y)	0,5737, 0,5737
Размер без сжатия	213,05 MB
Формат	TIFF
Тип источника	Общий
Тип пиксела	целое число без знака
Глубина пиксела	8 Бит

Picture 3. Features of orthophotoplane

Picture 4. Loading a raster in SASPLANET

In order to determine whether the raster data obtained from SASPLANET is correctly positioned, the weather conditions of the area being measured with the GPS device must be clear and good, and it is recommended to measure the contours of the land one by one. GPS device and compare it with the attributive data of boundaries obtained through orthophoto planes (pictures 5-6).

picture 5. GPS device menu picture 5. GPS device menu Figure 6. A
Figure 6. A view of the GPS view of the GPS device in action
device in action

Among the problems we may face in the process of using land resources and in the process of converting it to a digital view, due to the improper use of technical processing technology on the edge of arable land, waste land is in the status of cultivated land in the balance sheet of the farmer, and as a result, there is no benefit from using it in agriculture, the land user and the land owner misunderstandings arise between government agencies. There is no legal solution to this issue.

Summary

Through this article, the definition and permanent control of the farm boundaries based on fixed territorial objects, that is, ditches, ditches, field and highways on the edge of the field and various other fixed point boundaries, and in the case where the contours are divided into parts, the border marking with the placement of seasonal (temporary) ditches in the middle of the field suggested installation. The width and other dimensions of the ditch are determined based on the objective and subjective conditions of the area and contour.

As a result of the above work, the possibilities of achieving resolution of disputes between farms or other agricultural organizations were considered.

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